

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Arsenic(III) by Chloramine-T*

G. BABU RAO, A. KODANDA RAMAIAH and P. V. KRISHNA RAO**

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair

Manuscript received 21 February 1979, revised 21 November 1979, accepted 31 December 1979

The kinetics of oxidation of arsenic (III) by chloramine-T has been studied in an alkaline medium. The reaction is first order both in the substrate and in the oxidant. An inverse first order dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$ has been observed. The effect of varying the ionic strength on the reaction rate is found to be negligible. A decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. The energy and entropy of activation for the oxidation process are 42.7 KJ mol^{-1} and -109.3 JK^{-1} (at 273°K) respectively. The proposed mechanism involves an interaction between $\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2$ ion and *p*-toluene sulphochloramide in the rate determining step.

ALTHOUGH the oxidation kinetics of many organic compounds by Chloramine-T (CAT) have been studied extensively¹, similar studies on inorganic compounds are rather scanty. Mushran and coworkers² have reported the oxidation kinetics of hexacyanoferrate(II) by CAT. In the present communication, the results of our kinetic study on the oxidation of arsenic(III) by CAT are reported. Kinetic studies on the oxidation of arsenic(III) by some oxidising agents have been reported³⁻⁷ in the literature.

Experimental

Reagents : E. Merck (p.a) sample of CAT was used without purification. Aqueous solutions of appropriate strength were prepared and stored in black-coated bottles. The strength of the aqueous solution was ascertained by the iodometric method⁸.

Aqueous solution of sodium arsenite was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed sample of arsenious oxide (A.R., B.D.H.) in 1.0 *N* sodium hydroxide and finally neutralising the excess alkali by 1.0 *N* hydrochloric acid.

All other reagents were of acceptable grade purity. Methanol was purified by distilling twice. The reaction vessels were coated black to exclude photochemical effects.

Kinetic measurements : Requisite amounts of arsenic(III) and sodium hydroxide solutions were taken in a reaction vessel and were thermostated in an Ultra Cryostat (Remi, RK 701) maintained at 0° . The reaction was initiated by adding a measured aliquot of CAT which was also pre-thermostated to the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted CAT iodometrically at various time intervals. The pseudo-first order rate

constants (k_1) were calculated from the slopes of plots of $\log [\text{CAT}]$ versus time which were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Results

Stoichiometry : Reaction mixtures containing excess CAT over arsenic(III) and vice-versa were kept at 30° in the presence of sodium hydroxide ($4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) for 48 hours. An estimation of the unreacted CAT or arsenic(III) has shown that, in either case, one mole of arsenic(III) consumed one mole of CAT which is in accordance with the earlier reports⁹.

Effect of reactant concentration : Kinetic runs were carried out at different initial concentrations of the reactants (Table 1). The reaction is first order in CAT

TABLE I—EFFECT OF REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS

[NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, Temp: 0°C .		
[CAT] $\times 10^4 \text{ M}$	[As(III)] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
5.0	5.0	10.53
7.5	10.0	21.40
10.0	10.0	21.80
5.0	6.25	13.75
5.0	7.50	16.23
5.0	8.75	19.25
5.0	10.0	21.66
5.0	11.25	24.75
5.0	12.50	27.59

*Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists (1978), Waltair.

**for correspondence.

as is evident from the linearity of plots of $\log [\text{CAT}]$ versus time. The first order dependence in CAT is further confirmed by the constancy of the k_1 values at different initial $[\text{CAT}]$. The k_1 values were proportional to $[\text{As(III)}]$ at different initial $[\text{As(III)}]$. A plot of k_1 against $[\text{As(III)}]$ gives a straight line passing through the origin thus indicating the first order dependence on $[\text{As(III)}]$.

Effect of $[\text{OH}^-]$: The rate of the reaction decreases with an increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 2). The slope of the plot of $\log(k_1)$ versus $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ is nearly unity indicating an inverse first order dependence of the rate on $[\text{OH}^-]$.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ALKALI CONCENTRATION

[As(III)] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [CAT] = $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp : $0^\circ C$.						
[NaOH] $\times 10^3 M$	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	8.0	
$k_1 \times 10^4 s^{-1}$	10.53	7.83	6.42	5.30	4.73	

Effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant: The addition of sodium perchlorate to the reaction mixture in varying concentrations has without any significant influence on the rate. A decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium (increase in methanol content) increases the reaction rate (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT

[CAT] = $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, [As(III)] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [NaOH] = $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, Temp : $0^\circ C$

I, M	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
$k_1 \times 10^4 s^{-1}$	10.53	10.55	10.50	10.60	10.65	10.60
% Methanol (vol/vol) :		Nil	10	20	30	40
$k_1 \times 10^4 s^{-1}$		10.53	11.10	12.50	13.77	14.40

Effect of temperature: Kinetic runs were carried out at 0° , 5° and 10° and the corresponding k_1 values are : 10.53, 14.09 and $20.43 \times 10^{-4} S^{-1}$ respectively when $[\text{As(III)}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{CAT}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $[\text{OH}^-] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Arrhenius equation is found to be applicable in this temperature range which leads to $E_a^\ddagger = 42.7 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -109.3 \text{ JK}^{-1}$ at $273^\circ K$. respectively.

Discussion

The ionic strength and dielectric constant effects indicate that the reaction may be between an ion and a

dipole. CAT hydrolyses in aqueous solution in accordance with :

The various oxidising species may be CAT itself, *p*-toluene sulphochloramide and Cl^- ion. As the rate is inversely proportional to $[\text{OH}^-]$, it is believed that *p*-toluene sulphochloramide is the active oxidising species¹⁰.

Earlier, it has been shown that in alkaline medium arsenic(III), exists as different species viz : As(OH)_3 , AsO(OH)_2^- , $\text{AsO}_2(\text{OH})^{2-}$ and AsO_3^{3-} according to the following equilibria :

In this connection, it may be mentioned that in the oxidation of arsenic(III) by Fe(CN)_6^{3-} in a highly alkaline medium, Mushran *et al.*⁶ observed a first order dependence of rate on OH^- . They have proposed AsO_3^{3-} as the active species of the substrate. The present investigation is carried out in low alkaline conditions ($[\text{OH}^-] = 4.0 - 8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$). Further, the rate is inversely proportional to $[\text{OH}^-]$ as in the case of many other reactions of CAT.

In this study, the authors believe that the equilibrium(1) is involved in the concentration range of the $[\text{OH}^-]$ employed. Since the inverse dependence of the rate on $[\text{OH}^-]$ can be understood from the hydrolysis of CAT, the effect of $[\text{OH}^-]$ on equilibrium(1) may be negligible. So it may be assumed that the reaction may be between $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{SO}_2 \text{NHCl}$ and AsO(OH)_2^- ion. In light of the above observations, the following mechanism is proposed to explain the experimental results.

Applying steady state treatment to the intermediates and with the reasonable assumption that $k'_{-1}[\text{NaOH}] > k'_2[\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2^-]$, the rate law is :

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k'_1 k'_2 [\text{CAT}][\text{AsO}(\text{OH})_2^-]}{k'_{-1}[\text{NaOH}]}$$

which is in accordance with the experimental results.

Acknowledgement

GBR and AKR are grateful to the CSIR, New Delhi for the award of junior and senior research fellowships respectively.

References

1. M. M. CAMPBELL and G. JOHNSON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1978, 78, 65.

2. M. C. AGRAWAL and S. P. MUSHRAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 838.
3. R. E. DELURY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 71, 54.
4. F. H. WESTHEIMER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1949, 45, 419.
5. J. G. MASON and A. D. KOWLAK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1248.
6. M. C. AGRAWAL, V. K. JINDAL and S. P. MUSHRAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 1257.
7. B. B. PAL, D. C. MUKHERJEE and K. K. SENGUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 3433.
8. K. BOTTFGER and W. Z. BOTTFGER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1927, 70, 225.
9. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZYKA, "Newer Redox Titrants", Pergamon Press Ltd., London, Ed., 1965, p. 39.
10. E. BISHOP and V. J. JENNINGS, *Talanta*, 1958, 1, 989.